

Introducing portable digital devices into science museum outreach activities: how diverse can it be?

Who are we?

What is our motivation?

The donation

10 x Notebook Magalhães DUO (CeleronN2805-2GB-32-GB-Win 8.1 c/Off H&S) by jp.group

1st year project milestones

Indoor outreach activities

▲
Observation and
identification of
marine organisms

Creating multimedia
records during CCVALg's
school visits

▲
Microscopy workshop

Indoor outreach activities

◀ Sound workshop

Molecular Modeling ▶

◀ Holograms

Introduction to the 3D modelling ▶

Outdoor outreach activities

▲
Birdwatching and
vegetal invasive
species observation
and collection

Microplastic detection

▲
Dune ecology:
determination of
biodiversity index

Outdoor outreach activities

◀ Macroinvertebrates monitoring of water masses.

Life under a trunk ▶

◀ The beach through a magnifying glasses

Corporate “Peddy tablet” ▶

Some outdoor activities

◀ Nocturnal astronomical observations

Activities with thermal probe ▶

◀ Labcam Graph Challenge

Submarine acoustic measurement ▶

Other applications

After 1st year

Type of initiative	# events
Astronomical observation	5
Debate/assembly	3
Field activity	12
Hands on activity	31
Institutional event	15
Scientific communication	1

Field of knowledge	# events
Maths and Modelling	1
Physics and Chemistry	9
Earth Sciences	2
Space Sciences	6
Life Sciences	31
Social Sciences	3
Applied Sciences	13
History and Culture	3

1 Year | 54 Initiatives (17 indoor + 37 outdoor) | 3291 participants

Main reflections

1) Project with a regional impact that added value to the CCVAlg offer

- Origin of a group that interacted with the devices in CCVAlg
- Local of an outdoor activity with the devices

2) Informal education environments like science museums are interesting to ITC pilots because:

- ▶ No pressure of formal curricula or evaluation moments
- ▶ Flexibility for testing design and implementation
- ▶ Easy access to a large number of testers
- ▶ Financially sustainable
- ▶ Good for activities' development

Further developments

Inclusion of new devices and/or new software under consideration
Involve other partners in the project

Thank You!